

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Benzamide by Silver(II), Cobalt(III) and Manganese(III) Ions in Aqueous Perchlorate Medium

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The kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of benzamide by silver(II), cobalt(III) and manganese(III) have been investigated in aqueous perchloric acid. It is found that the principal reactive species of aqua-metal ions is M^{n+} which has been shown to exist in equilibrium with $MOH^{(n-1)+}$. The rate of the title reaction has a first order dependence both on M^{n+} and benzamide. The rate is accelerated by increasing $[H^+]$ but unaffected by $NaClO_4$. Four moles of oxidant are consumed per mole of benzamide and the rate equation, based upon the experimental data, takes the form

$$-\frac{1}{[M^{n+}]} \frac{d[M^{n+}]}{dt} = 4(k[H^+] + k'') [\text{benzamide}]$$

The free radical mechanism consistent with these results have been suggested and the associated thermodynamic parameters discussed.

The kinetics of oxidation of benzamide by the highly oxidizing aqua-cations Ag^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Mn^{3+} in aqueous perchlorate medium show that the general mechanism involves the rapid formation of intermediate complexes between the aqua-cation M^{n+} and benzamide which then decomposes slowly to give products. Similar intermediate complexes are also suggested for the oxidation of some amides by various metal ions¹⁻⁵.

In view of the biological importance of amides, the study of electron transfer reactions with amides has been undertaken by us. We have reported some electron transfer reactions with aliphatic amides and now we are extending these studies to aromatic amides, the aqua-cations, Ag^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Mn^{3+} being used as oxidants. A kinetic treatment of the reaction of benzamide with Ag^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Mn^{3+} is reported in this paper.

Experimental

Materials: Benzamide (New MCC, England) was used as such. Perchloric acid (70%, E. Merck) was used to maintain the $[H^+]$. Anhydrous sodium perchlorate (Koch Light) was used to maintain the ionic strength. All other reagents used were AnalaR chemicals of certified purity. The preparation and standardization of aqua silver(II), cobalt(III) and manganese(III) ions in perchloric acid solution has been described¹⁻⁵.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetics were followed under pseudo first order conditions with benzamide in excess. Before using the titrimetric method for rate measurements it was ensured that the concentration of benzamide in the reaction mixtures would

not alter the titrimetric readings. The observed first order rate constants, k_{obs} , with respect to $[M^{n+}]$ was obtained from the gradients of the linear plots of $\log [M^{n+}]$ against time. The reproducibility of k_{obs} values in repeated runs was within 3-4% and the mean values are reported in the tables. The linearity itself extended well beyond two half lives of the reaction indicating that none of the products formed during the reaction affected the rate. The decay of $[M^{n+}]$ was measured iodometrically as described earlier⁵. The temperature was controlled to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by a thermostated water bath.

Stoichiometry and product study: Reaction mixtures having different concentration ratios of benzamide and M^{n+} at different acidities were prepared and placed in a thermostated water bath maintained at temperatures at which kinetic studies were carried out. The unreacted M^{n+} was estimated after completion of the reaction. It can be seen that the average value of $\Delta[M^{n+}]/\Delta[\text{benzamide}]$ is 4.0. This stoichiometric ratio was also confirmed by gasometric studies. The volumes of CO_2 and O_2 evolved during the course of the reaction were measured quantitatively and it confirmed the above stoichiometry (Table 1). Hence, the stoichiometric equation for the oxidation reactions could be expressed by eq. (1).

The presence of ammonia and phenol in the reaction mixture was confirmed by standard analytical methods. Benzoic acid was also formed during the course of reaction and its presence was confirmed in the reaction product spectrophotometrically as it gives a maximum at 230 nm. However, quantitative

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF THE GASOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS^a AT 23° FOR Co(III), AT 29° FOR Mn(III) AND AT 32° FOR Ag(II)

[Benzamide] M	[M ⁿ⁺] M × 10 ⁻²	CO ₂ (ml)	Over 40% KOH O ₂ (ml)
		Ag ²⁺	
0.02	0.4	2.2	1.1
	0.6	2.9	1.3
	0.8	3.8	1.9
		Co ³⁺	
0.02	0.2	2.1	0.9
	0.3	2.8	1.5
	0.4	3.2	1.6
		Mn ³⁺	
0.02	0.2	2.7	1.2
	0.3	3.6	1.8
	0.4	4.4	2.3

^a All experiments were performed with [HClO₄] = 3.0 M and μ = 3.5 M.

estimation of benzoic acid at 230 nm was not very satisfactory.

Results and Discussion

Upon carrying out the kinetic experiments under pseudo first order conditions (with at least 10 fold excess of benzamide) at constant [H⁺] and ionic strength, plots of log [oxidant] against time showed good linearity upto 90% conversion. In Fig. 1, the k_{obs} are plotted against benzamide concentration at constant oxidant concentration, [H⁺] and ionic strength. The good linearity of the plots indicates that the reaction is first order with respect to [benzamide].

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} against [benzamide].

The rate measurements were made over 2.50-5.00 M perchloric acid at constant ionic strength (5.00 M, NaClO₄). Later, these rate measurements were repeated at other temperatures. The results indicated that k_{obs} increased with increasing [H⁺]. The plots of k_{obs} against [H⁺] were linear (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Plots of k_{obs} against [H⁺].

The correlation between k_{obs} and [Mⁿ⁺] is discussed in more detail later. The presence of lower valency cation Ag⁺, Co³⁺ and Mn²⁺ in reaction mixture did not cause an appreciable effect on the rate parameters. It appears that no reverse reactions or equilibria involving Ag⁺, Co³⁺ and Mn²⁺ are significant. Similarly an increase in ionic strength from 0.50-5.00 M (NaClO₄) had no effect on any of the reaction rates.

The values of the rate constants at three temperatures and at various [H⁺] are reported in Table 2 together with the corresponding values of the enthalpy and entropy of activation. The value of enthalpy of activation is relatively high in the case of aquamanganese(III) and the slow rate of oxidation in it is therefore due to the higher activation enthalpy.

The negative entropy of activation suggests that the charge changes here on the activation complex results in the freezing of solvent molecules. Although there is no evidence here for the participation of complexes (PhCONH₂-Mⁿ⁺), these cannot be fully excluded. However, the relative redox reactivity of Ag²⁺, Co³⁺ and Mn³⁺ with benzamide may be merely a reflection of the order of the respective E⁰ values (2.0, 1.95 and 1.56 V, respectively)⁶⁻⁸.

In view of the kinetic features described earlier, the mechanism (2)–(9) for the oxidation of benzamide may be suggested. Since the hydrolysis rate constant of C₆H₅CONH₂ is 1.0 × 10⁻⁹ sec⁻¹ at 25[±]0.1⁰, the predominant form of benzamide would be C₆H₅CONH₂.

With regard to Ag²⁺, Co³⁺ and Mn³⁺ species, since perchlorate solutions have been employed and since the rate is independent of the increase of perchlorate ion, there is little possibility of complexes of the metal species being very reactive^{10,11}. Another possibility for the metal species to exist in the hydrolyzed form has been indicated in the oxidation of hydroxylamine¹², vanadium(IV)¹³ and aliphatic organic compounds^{14,15} (eq. 4). The value of K_b for the equilibrium in eq. (2)

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AND k_{obs} FOR THE OXIDATION OF BENZAMIDE BY Ag^{2+} , Co^{3+} AND Mn^{3+} AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ACIDITIES

[Benzamide]=0.02 M ; μ =5.5 M

Temperature °C	k_{obs} (sec ⁻¹) at [HClO ₄] M				
	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0
Ag²⁺					
5	1.98	1.65	1.86	2.20	2.45
10	1.72	1.85	2.23	2.50	2.70
15	2.73	3.25	3.50	4.00	4.69
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mole ⁻¹)	42.3 ± 8.6	42.5 ± 9.2	39.5 ± 7.3	38.3 ± 5.8	38.7 ± 7.3
ΔS^\ddagger (Jk ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)	-145.4 ± 30.9	-143.1 ± 32.0	-123.9 ± 24.8	-161.2 ± 19.8	-148.3 ± 26.0
Co³⁺					
10	0.90	1.16	1.30	1.42	1.57
15	1.31	1.41	1.49	1.53	1.65
20	1.79	1.81	2.09	2.53	3.12
ΔH (kJ mole ⁻¹)	42.0 ± 1.8	38.0 ± 1.3	40.0 ± 4.5	41.6 ± 7.2	40.3 ± 5.5
ΔS (Jk ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)	-153.0 ± 1.9	-201.0 ± 4.3	-201.6 ± 14.5	-187.9 ± 24.6	-201.5 ± 5.3
Mn³⁺					
52	1.16	1.48	1.51	1.70	1.90
57	1.52	1.75	2.00	2.19	2.76
62	2.48	2.80	3.24	3.58	4.24
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mole ⁻¹)	60.9 ± 4.5	54.7 ± 8.2	66.3 ± 5.6	64.1 ± 6.7	67.5 ± 3.3
ΔS^\ddagger (Jk ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)	-115.4 ± 13.0	-131.0 ± 25.3	-96.0 ± 17.5	-101.9 ± 20.7	-89.8 ± 9.4

has been found to vary from 0.1 to 0.7 at I=5.6 M¹⁶ for Ag²⁺, 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ 1⁷ for Co³⁺ and 0.5 to 1.5 at I=4.0 M for Mn³⁺ 1⁸.

Hence the predominant form of the oxidant in 4.0 M HClO₄ would be Mⁿ⁺_{aq}⁺, but M⁽ⁿ⁻¹⁾⁺OH would also be present. If Mⁿ⁺_{aq}⁺ is reactive, there would be change in the rate proportional to the concentration of Mⁿ⁺_{aq}⁺ with the increase of HClO₄. However, if both Mⁿ⁺_{aq}⁺ and M⁽ⁿ⁻¹⁾⁺OH are involved, there would be a small increase in the rate as found in the present investigation. Thus Mⁿ⁺_{aq}⁺ and M⁽ⁿ⁻¹⁾⁺OH are reactive species in the oxidation of benzamide.

In fact, by comparing the present data with previously studied reactions of these metal ions where complex formation occurs, it seems reasonable to suggest that water exchange in the coordination sphere of these metal ions is not rate-determining in the reactions under investigation.

In the experimental conditions used here, benzamide will be largely protonated, because we use high concentration of perchloric acid which is required to stabilize the aqua-metal ions in solution. The protonated and unprotonated benzamide give rise to the equilibria (3)

But the more reacting form of the amide in our studies is the protonated benzamide. The pK value of benzamide in highly acidic media is 0.99 at 25° 1⁹. It is therefore expected that the benzamide is almost completely protonated in our experiments.

The interaction between metal ion and protonated benzamide appears to be the more rate deter-

mining process. The reaction sequence as given below [eqs (2)–(9)] is consistent with the experimental data.

$$\text{Rate of reaction} = k_4 [PhC(OH) = \overset{+}{N}H_2] [M^{n+}] + k_5 [PhC(OH) = \overset{+}{N}H_2] [M^{(n-1)+}OH] \quad \dots (10)$$

Using equilibria (2) and (3)

$$\text{Rate of reaction} = k' [PhCONH_2] [H^+] [M^{n+}] + k'' [PhCONH_2] [M^{n+}] \quad \dots (11)$$

where $k' = K_a k_4$ and $k'' = k_1 k_5 K_a$

or

$$-\frac{1}{4} \frac{d[M^{n+}]}{dt} = k'[H^+] + k''[\text{benzamide}] [M^{n+}] \quad \dots (12)$$

or

$$-\frac{1}{M^{n+}} \frac{d[M^{n+}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} \quad \dots(13)$$

where

$$k_{\text{obs}} = 4(k'[H^+] + k'') [\text{benzamide}] \quad \dots(14)$$

$$M^{n+} = \text{Ag}^{2+}, \text{Co}^{3+} \text{ and } \text{Mn}^{3+}$$

This explains the dependence of the reaction rate with respect to benzamide, metal ions, hydrogen ion, sodium perchlorate and lower valency cations. The values of k' and k'' for different oxidants have been graphically evaluated and are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF k' AND k'' CALCULATED GRAPHICALLY

Oxidants	Temp. °C	k'	k''
Co(III)	10	2.40	3.10
Mn(III)	52	3.75	6.25
Ag(II)	10	5.80	6.50

[Benzamide] = 0.02 M.

The acceleration of the rate of the reaction by increasing the concentration of the hydrogen ion indicates that only protonated benzamide is reacting with the metal ions.

However, the interaction of $M^{(n-1)+}OH$ with amide cannot be ruled out, as the plots of k_{obs} against $[H^+]$ give positive intercepts. But it is probably only a minor reaction path.

The protonated benzamide-metal ion complex, [eq (4)] is considered to yield products by reacting with water molecules. The results would be consistent with the reactions represented by eqs (2) to (9), where the formation of free radicals is confirmed by the fact that addition of traces of iodine enhances the oxidation rate. It is probable due to the formation of hydroxylamine which reacts rapidly with Ag^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Mn^{3+} (Ref. 21, 22).

In the presence of iodine, almost 9-10 moles of metal ions are consumed per mole of benzamide. Therefore, the reaction stoichiometry is totally changed in presence of iodine. Free radicals in the reaction mixtures were also confirmed by adding acrylonitrile which polymerizes in the system under study.

In the case of benzamide, it is postulated that the electron transfer from the metal results in the formation of benzoic acid which is subsequently rapidly oxidised to give phenol and carbon dioxide involving free radicals. The possibility of the involvement of any other reaction path is ruled out by the fact that the ratio of moles of CO_2 evolved to the moles of O_2 evolved does not depend on the acidity and concentrations of benzamide and metal ions used. (Table 1; results of gasometric measurements

at different acidities and amide concentrations are not included to avoid repetition). It indicates that there is only one reaction path and that is the interaction of protonated benzamide with metal ion species. We also observe large negative ΔS^\ddagger in the oxidation of benzamide by Ag^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Mn^{3+} indicating that the lowest step may involve an interaction of like charges. The k_{obs} follow the sequence $k_A > k_C > k_M$, where k stands for the observed rate constant for the oxidation of benzamide and subscripts A, C and M stand for Ag^{2+} , Co^{3+} and Mn^{3+} , respectively. The oxidation potential of the aqueous metal ions follow the sequence $E_{\text{Ag}^{2+}}^0 > E_{\text{Co}^{3+}}^0 > E_{\text{Mn}^{3+}}^0$. Therefore, the observed order is the most expected one.

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